

COMPETENCIES REQUIRED BY THE TEACHER IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF EDUCATIONAL COMPETENCIES THROUGH WORDS WITH CONNOTATIVE MEANING

Maxkamova Guluzroxon

a teacher of the Department of methods of primary
education of Andijan State pedagogical Institute
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Educational and teaching competence is the sum of competencies in language learning in the activities of the learner to obtain and develop independent knowledge and includes logical, methodological and general educational tasks related to the use of modern educational technologies. Educational competence encompasses a variety of important components including: educational competence is a psychological as well as an educational category. This competence is the ability of the student to perform tasks related to the learning activity and the ability to use it effectively, which assumes the performance of a number of tasks specific to the student.

In the ever-evolving landscape of education, the role of a teacher extends far beyond mere knowledge transmission; it encompasses the cultivation of critical competencies that empower students to navigate an increasingly complex world. Central to this mission is the teacher's ability to effectively harness the power of language, particularly through words imbued with connotative meaning. These nuanced expressions not only convey information but also evoke emotions, shape perceptions, and foster deeper understanding.

As educators strive to develop essential skills in their students—such as critical thinking, creativity, and emotional intelligence—they must themselves embody a rich repertoire of linguistic competencies. This involves not just the selection of appropriate vocabulary but also an awareness of the emotional and cultural resonances that words can carry. By mastering the art of connotation, teachers can create a more engaging and inclusive learning environment, encouraging students to explore ideas with depth and sensitivity.

In this exploration of the competencies required by teachers, we will delve into the significance of connotative language in educational settings, examining how it can enhance communication, inspire motivation, and ultimately contribute to the holistic development of students' educational competencies.

Connotation refers to the emotional and associative meanings that words carry beyond their literal definitions. It influences how messages are perceived and can significantly impact communication in educational settings.

2. Importance of Connotative Language in Education

- Emotional Engagement: Words with positive connotations can inspire and motivate students, while negative connotations may discourage or alienate them.

- Cultural Sensitivity: Understanding connotations helps teachers navigate diverse classrooms, respecting cultural differences and fostering inclusivity.

- Critical Thinking: Encouraging students to analyze the connotations of words deepens their critical thinking skills, as they learn to consider context and perspective.

1. Motivation and Encouragement

- Example: Using the word "challenge" instead of "problem."

- Connotation: "Challenge" implies an opportunity for growth and learning, while "problem" may suggest something negative or difficult to overcome.

- Application: A teacher might say, "This math challenge will help us develop our problem-solving skills," fostering a positive mindset.

2. Feedback and Assessment

- Example: Describing a student as "developing" rather than "struggling."

- Connotation: "Developing" suggests progress and potential, while "struggling" may evoke feelings of defeat.

- Application: Instead of saying, "You're struggling with this concept," a teacher might say, "You're developing your understanding of this concept," which encourages perseverance.

3. Classroom Environment

- Example: Referring to rules as "guidelines" rather than "restrictions."

- Connotation: "Guidelines" suggests flexibility and support, whereas "restrictions" implies limitations.

- Application: A teacher could frame classroom expectations as, "These guidelines will help us create a supportive learning environment," promoting a sense of community.

4. Encouraging Participation

- Example: Using the term "contribute" instead of "participate."

- Connotation: "Contribute" emphasizes the value of each student's input, while "participate" can feel more passive.

- Application: A teacher might say, "I encourage everyone to contribute their ideas during our discussion," fostering a sense of ownership and value.

Incorporating connotative language into educational practices is essential for developing key competencies among students. By choosing words carefully,

educators can enhance emotional engagement, foster inclusivity, and promote critical thinking. This nuanced approach to language not only enriches the learning environment but also equips students with the skills they need to thrive in a complex world.

The list of used literature:

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